

A Holistic Behavioral, Clinical, and Environmental Assessment Questionnaire for Companion Animals

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Introduction

The following questionnaire is a multidimensional and structured tool for obtaining a comprehensive history and creating an integrated clinical record in veterinary medical centers. This tool has been designed based on real clinical needs, practical experience in veterinary medical environments, and a review of relevant and authoritative scientific sources. It is designed to prevent the unwanted omission of important information and incomplete and one-dimensional impressions and ultimately contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the animal's condition, facilitate the process of diagnosis and information analysis, and subsequently improve the quality of clinical decision-making.

General structure

This questionnaire is organized in three sections (three supplementary booklets):

A) Instructions for using the questionnaire: This section describes the general principles of use and tips and suggestions for how to present, ask questions, and interpret information.

B) Questionnaire I: The information in this section is essentially the basis for the assessment. This form is completed by the client/caregiver and consists of twelve systematic sections; the titles of these sections have been removed from the form itself to avoid bias.

1. Identification information and basic characteristics
2. Family history and social structure
3. Housing conditions and living environment
4. Health history and referral to medical centers
5. Sleep pattern and daily activity
6. Nutritional status
7. Oral health
8. Review of time spent alone and separation anxiety
9. Self-directed behaviors
10. Social behaviors and interactions
11. Clinical status and physical health
12. Initial summary by the caregiver

c) Questionnaire II: This section is completed by the treating veterinarian and treatment staff and consists of five main sections that focus on clinical observations, professional evaluation, diagnostic decisions, and follow-up plan. By recording the clinical findings obtained from the first visit and clinical observations and examinations in a structured manner, it will be possible to follow up, refer, and collaborate more effectively in the field.

Rationale and Necessity for Using the Questionnaire

This questionnaire aims to create a structured framework for collecting information related to the physical, behavioral, environmental, and lifestyle status of the companion animal. In many clinical cases, especially in complex, chronic, or multifactorial cases, seemingly insignificant information (such as sleep patterns, ambient light, social interactions, or gradual behavioral changes) plays a key role in reaching a correct diagnosis. This information is usually not fully presented in the oral history by the patient due to lack of time, high stress in emergency or semi-emergency situations, high caseload, and veterinarian fatigue from repeatedly stating educational and basic matters, or other issues.

Using this questionnaire helps the veterinarian to receive essential information in a systematic and comparable manner; avoid wasting time on repeated visits for basic questions; identify hidden or gradual patterns of behavioral and physical changes; and make decisions for additional examinations or more targeted specialist referrals.

This form is particularly helpful in behavioral or psychosomatic cases, chronic or recurrent diseases, cases involving multiple body systems simultaneously, and referrals involving more than one veterinarian or department.

Completing this questionnaire not only increases clinical accuracy but also creates a standardized, auditable record, allowing for tracking of clinical progress over time and comparison of changes in subsequent visits.

Contrary to popular belief, the initial time spent completing this form will, in practice, lead to reduced follow-up visit times, reduced repetition of questions, increased quality of referrals between departments, and increased veterinarian and patient satisfaction.

Intended users

This questionnaire is designed for use in clinics, hospitals, and centers providing services to companion animals, and specialist veterinarians, general veterinarians, residents, and other members of the veterinary medical staff, can use it.

Practical suggestion

Besides clinical and behavioral assessment, this questionnaire also allows for the identification of training needs of the clients. Based on the recorded responses and the veterinarian's observations, cases that indicate a lack of knowledge, maintenance errors, or misconceptions about the behavioral, nutritional, environmental, and health needs of the animal can be referred to an independent training department. With the aim of providing standard, practical training tailored to the conditions of each animal and family, this department can be formed as a separate and parallel section to the clinical and therapeutic section, by trained individuals and specialized personnel, and in a calm environment appropriate to the welfare facilities for the animal and the client. Providing training separately from the clinical visit, at a lower cost and with reduced time pressure on the veterinarian, may enhance the quality of communication with the client, improve mutual understanding, increase adherence to treatment recommendations, and ultimately improve animal welfare. Basic and comprehensive training can be provided in the form of brochures, educational videos, in-person explanation and training of protocols, answering general questions and maintenance methods, introducing the trainer, introducing appropriate basic equipment, and explaining post-treatment care protocols. A very important point for improving the performance of this department is continuous and permanent professional supervision of the performance of the personnel of this department by supervisors specializing in each field, and updating information and carefully reviewing protocols and brochures with reputable scientific authorities. Any application of personal opinion, non-scientific experience, non-specialized prescription of drugs and supplements by a non-veterinarian, commercial and biased introduction, incorrect training, or imposed and inappropriate treatment can undermine the efficiency of this department from an ethical, legal, and professional perspective.

Instructions

A) Instructions for presenting and completing the form

In order to obtain the best results from the present questionnaire and the highest degree of cooperation from the client, in addition to understanding the basic and specialized principles, the presentation method and tone of communication with the client are also very important.

To increase the accuracy of the answers and reduce the client's psychological stress, it is recommended that this questionnaire be presented before the clinical visit and in a calm and stress-free environment by trained personnel with public relations and high emotional intelligence. The presenter must be familiar with the details of the form and have awareness of the purpose of the form and its necessity so that, if necessary, be able to patiently answer all questions and doubts or help in completing the form for people with low literacy levels or people who are unable to complete the form themselves.

The provider's tone should be calm, empathetic, supportive, and without bias of any kind. The client should feel safe and not feel like being interrogated or tested. It is necessary to reassure the patient

with tone and gestures that no judgment is made about the individual's personality based on these questions and that this form is completely confidential and its information will not be made available to any third party.

Methods such as sending the form electronically (email/messaging) after registering the appointment, asking the patient to arrive about 45 to 60 minutes early for the first visit, allowing the patient to complete the form at home and hand it in on the day of the visit, or considering a dedicated waiting room with amenities and a quiet environment with appropriate lighting for filling out the form according to the patient's needs or requests are suggested.

Given the length of the questionnaire, it is necessary to emphasize that this questionnaire is completed only on the first visit and will only be updated in subsequent visits. It is also necessary to explain the necessity of this questionnaire, its benefits, and the great importance of honesty in it without any judgment.

Suggested phrases to introduce the form include:

- 1) *"This form helps us get to know your little one better and allows the visit to focus on the real problem."*
- 2) *"Many of these questions may seem simple, but they are very important for diagnosis."*
- 3) *"If you are unsure about something, it is okay to write, 'I don't know.'"*
- 4) *"This form is designed to provide you with better service and to better understand possible problems and is completely confidential."*
- 5) *"There are no wrong or right answers."*

It should be noted that the presentation of this form by impatient or uninformed staff can be ineffective or even ruin the entire process. Staff should be prepared to explain questions in simpler language if needed and use examples for better understanding, help illiterate or elderly clients, and create a sense of companionship without rushing. Avoid rushing, standing to fill in, or filling in verbally at the reception desk.

The answers to this questionnaire are not considered a diagnosis by themselves but can help the veterinarian identify abnormal patterns, decide on further investigation, and make targeted referrals to specialized departments.

B) Evaluation Instructions

After the first form is completed by the client and the initial examination and visit, the second questionnaire is provided to the veterinarian, who, after reviewing the answers to the first form and the results of the examinations, reports his analysis and diagnosis for referral and follow-up. Referrals should be recorded in the file, even if the client does not follow up.

Questionnaire section	Symptoms/Responses of the client	Immediate action in the clinic	Follow-up/Record in the file	Referral suggestion
<i>Section 1:</i> Basic Profiles	Species, breed, age, sex, appearance, general temperament	Accurate record keeping, attention to specific needs	Check for mood changes at follow-up visits	Referral in case of severe temperament discrepancy with breed or age standard
<i>Section 2:</i> Login/Member ship Information	entry, date of entry, interaction with other animals and family members	Note interactions and dependencies	Check for changes at follow-up visits	Provide training to the client to manage interactions
<i>Section 3:</i> Living Environment	Living space, dedicated space, toys, light, scent/smoke	Create a suitable and safe environment, manage stimuli	Record information and match animal behavior	Educate the client in case of lack of facilities
<i>Section 4:</i> Health and Medical History	Bathing, nails, hair, vaccines, deworming pills, surgeries, microchip	Complete review of health and medical history, vaccination and antiparasitic treatment if needed	Record in file for periodic follow-up	Referral to a specialized veterinarian in case of medical problems or delayed vaccination
<i>Section 5:</i> Life Cycle and Sleep	Sleep and wake times, activity, play and attention demands, ambient light	Proper activity and sleep planning, modify the environment	Track behavioral changes and sleep cycles	Educate the client in case of sleep abnormalities or high energy
<i>Section 6:</i> Nutrition	Type and number of meals, water, food and treats, playing with food, food cravings	Review nutrition and diet, modify in case of problems	Record in file for health and weight assessment	Provide nutritional guidance and training to the client in case of appetite or food craving problems
<i>Section 7:</i> Mouth and Teeth	Brushing, bleeding, bad breath, scaling	Dental examination, patient education	Record in file and follow-up examinations	Referral to a veterinarian or dentist in case of serious problems
<i>Section 8:</i> Time Alone at Home	Duration of alone time, behavior upon return of the visitor, damage to property, neighbor complaints	Provide patient education, reduce animal stress	Record in file for follow-up	Referral to a behaviorist in case of aggression or severe anxiety
<i>Section 9:</i> Self- Directed Behavior	Licking, scratching, hair/feather pulling, tail play, mirror interaction	Examine mental, physical and skin condition	Record in file for follow-up	Referral to a veterinarian or behaviorist in case of severe repetition or self-harm
<i>Section 10:</i> Behavior and Temperament	Voice, aggression, following, periods of mood swings, punishment	Relaxing measures, record behavior	Track changes and evaluate results	Referral to a behaviorist in case of severe or dangerous behaviors
<i>Section 11:</i> Physical Health	Gaiting, fatigue, salivation, masses, urination/defecation, eyes, nose, breathing, weight, skin, digestion, balance, tremors, nutrition, wounds	Complete examination, record clinical symptoms, take immediate action if needed	Follow-up visits	Referral to a specialized vet/lab in case of severe or unusual problems

The above table shows a general summary of the initial form assessment. It should be noted that the final decision and diagnosis are entirely the responsibility of the treating veterinarian and are based on their specialized knowledge.

To facilitate and reduce the problems of the physical file, forms and tables can be uploaded as an electronic file by adding the referral number, next visit date, and educational notes to the table and referred to specialists in an automated manner:

Interdepartmental referral should be consistent with the specialist explanation and initial assessment form and should only be sent to the relevant department if necessary, with confidentiality maintained and through personnel or automation. Avoid giving the physical file to the client.

Reference to the education department by the treating veterinarian should be based on need to avoid wasting the client's time and money.

In the case of behavioral problems, including anxiety and aggression, it is strongly recommended that the initial/internal examination be carried out according to the protocol and under the supervision/presence of a veterinary behaviorist.

Re-evaluating and, where feasible, designing or redesigning veterinary hospitals in accordance with standard veterinary hospital engineering protocols, using appropriate lighting, spatial layout, and proper equipment selection/use is a critical issue worldwide, particularly for animals with a history of moderate to severe anxiety during clinic visits. Regular provision of updated, advanced training courses for each veterinary specialty, the use of comprehensive and modern history-taking tools, and the implementation of appropriate equipment along with specialized, well-trained personnel are recommended to achieve better diagnostic and therapeutic outcomes.

If you have any questions or would like more information about this questionnaire, you can contact the author by email.

Questionnaire I

Clinic Information (to be completed by the clinic):

Clinic/Hospital Name:

Name of Treating Veterinarian:

Date of First Visit:

Case Number:

****Dear Caregiver,**

The questionnaire you are about to submit has been prepared to gain a more detailed understanding of your companion's living conditions, physical condition, and behavior so that the treatment team can provide you with more appropriate and effective services.

- This form is completed only once, but its information will be used in future visits; therefore, please answer all questions carefully and honestly.
- If you do not know the exact answer to a question or are not sure, indicate options such as "I do not know" or "I am not sure." Please do not leave any section blank.
- All information entered by this center is considered confidential and will only be used to improve the examination and treatment process.

Thank you for your cooperation.**

(To be filled in by the client)

Client Information:	
First and Last Name:	Contact Number:
Address (optional):	Email:
Section One:	
1) His/her name:	
2) Class (species included)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Mammal: <input type="checkbox"/> Bird: <input type="checkbox"/> Reptile: <input type="checkbox"/> Amphibian: <input type="checkbox"/> Fish:	
<input type="checkbox"/> Other:	
Breed / Mutant (if known):/ <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know	
* (Example: Shih Tzu, DSH, Scottish Fold, Lutino, Albino)	
3) Age:	
<input type="checkbox"/> Less than 6 months <input type="checkbox"/> 6 months to 1 year <input type="checkbox"/> 1 to 3 years <input type="checkbox"/> 3 to 7 years	
<input type="checkbox"/> More than 7 years <input type="checkbox"/> Not sure	
4) Sex:	
<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Unspecified / Undiagnosed	
5) Has he/she been neutered?	
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know	

6) Notable appearance feature (if any):

* (Example: specific color, unusual hair or feathers, two-colored eyes, specific ears, etc.)

7) In your opinion, his/her general temperament is:

Calm Playful Kind Shy / withdrawn Nervous / irritable Indifferent

Variable (sometimes calm, sometimes nervous) Additional comments:

8) If you were to describe his/her temperament in one sentence:

.....

Section Two:

1) How did he/she enter the family?

Purchased Adopted Found (street / outdoor environment)

Rescued (accident, emergency, etc.) Other:

2) At what age did he/she join your household?

From birth Less than 2 months 2 to 6 months More than 6 months

As an adult I don't know exactly

3) Do you have any other pets at home?

No Yes (please specify) a) Number:

b) Species and breed (if known):

c) Family relationship: Sister/brother Parent Child None

4) How does he/she interact with other pets?

We do not have any other pets Completely friendly Indifferent

Competitive or jealous Conflicting and fighting

Variable (sometimes good, sometimes bad) Additional explanation:

5) How does he/she interact with family members?

Has a good relationship with all members Is close to only one or a few specific people

Reacts negatively to some people Distances himself/herself from most people

Strongly dependent on one person Additional explanation:

6) How does he/she react to new people or guests?

- Friendly and quickly adapts Curious but cautious Indifferent
 Fearful and hides Shows aggression Depends on the situation
 Becomes dependent on the client (clings, does not separate)

Additional explanation:

7) How often does he/she usually encounter unfamiliar people or guests?

- Almost every day Several times a week Occasionally Rarely Almost never

8) If he/she have a specific or intense reaction to people or situations, please explain:

.....

Section Three:

1) Where is he/she kept most of the time?

- Indoors (with family members) Separate room Yard or outdoor space
 Cage/container Aquarium/terrarium
 Other:

2) Does the animal have a dedicated resting area?

- No Yes (please explain):
a) Approximate size of the space: square meters/centimeters
b) Type of floor or bedding: Carpet Soil Paper Plastic Other:

3) animal's food, water, and litter boxes are:

- Dedicated and separate from other animals Shared with other animals
 Variable (depending on conditions)

4) What is the material of the food and water containers or storage area?

- Steel Plastic Ceramic/glass Wooden Other:

5) Does he/she have toys?

- No Yes (Type): Ready-made animal toys Household items (slippers, cloth, etc.)
 Natural objects (wood, rocks, pine nuts, etc.) Variable

6) How much does he/she usually play with toys or the surrounding environment daily?

- Very little Moderate A lot Only in the presence of the caregiver
 Does not play at all

7) How much is he/she exposed to the following in its living environment? *(Select multiple options if possible)*

- a) Cigarette smoke: None Little Much
- b) Perfumes and air fresheners: None Little Much
- c) Detergents: None Little Much
- d) Lots of noise: None Little Much

8) Is he/she able to move freely in the living space?

- Yes, freely Limited (hours of the day) Very limited Fully enclosed

9) If you think his/her living environment is not ideal, please explain:

.....

Section Four:

1) Does he/she get a bath?

- No Yes (please specify): a) How often?.....
- b) Wash with: Special shampoo Human detergent Water Other:
 - c) Drying method: Towel Hair dryer Spontaneous
 - d) Animal's reaction during bath: Calm Anxious Resisting Aggressive

2) Are the nails trimmed?

- No Yes (please specify): a) How often?
- b) Animal's reaction: Cooperating Resisting Fearful Biting/Grabbing

3) How is the hair/fur handled?

- Not trimmed Trimmed: a) How often?.....
- b) Location: At the groomer/clinic At home
 - c) Animal reaction: Calm Anxious Aggressive Needs restraint

4) Has he/she ever been vaccinated?

- No Not sure Yes: a) At what age did it start?
- b) When was the last vaccination?

5) Do you use anti-parasitic drugs (internal or external)?

- No Yes: a) How often?
- b) In what form?

6) Have you ever seen any signs of parasitic infection?

- No Yes (please explain):

7) Has he/she ever had a serious illness?

- No Yes (please specify): a) Type of disease:
b) From age to.....
c) Type and location of treatment:

8) Has he/she ever had surgery?

- No Yes: a) Type of surgery: Neutering Orthopedic surgery Internal Other
b) Age at the time of surgery:

9) How is he/she transported usually?

- Special box Basket / cage Free (without enclosure) Other:

10) Reaction during transportation:

- Calm Anxious Aggressive Nausea / tremors

Additional comments:

11) Does he/she have a microchip or identification collar?

- No Yes (microchip) Yes (collar) Yes (both)

12) How does he/she react to the treatment conditions?

- a) During injection or vaccination: Calm Anxious Resisting Aggressive
b) During examination by veterinarian: Cooperates Stresses Screams/attacks/tries to escape
c) Does he/she have an unpleasant experience with the clinic or treatment? No Yes (please explain)

Section Five:

1) What time does he/she usually sleep?

- No specific time Around pm Goes to bed early most days Up most nights

2) Does he/she wake up at night?

- No Yes, sometimes Yes, frequently

3) What does he/she usually do if he/she wakes up in the middle of the night?

- Walks Makes noises Demands attention or food Is restless Does not wake up

4) Does he/she sleep during the day?

- No Yes, short Yes, long

Section Six:

1) What does he/she usually eat? (*You can choose more than one option*)

- Homemade food (cooked, no seasoning) Ready-made dry food
 More prepared food A combination of homemade and prepared food
 Raw food Uses your own food

Additional explanation:

2) How many times a day would you feed him/her?

- No specific time Food is constantly available to him
 Specific time: once 2 times more than 2 times

3) What time is food usually given?

4) What do you think is his/her appetite?

- Very good Normal Poor Variable (sometimes a lot, sometimes a little)

5) Have you noticed any changes in his appetite recently?

- No Yes (please explain):

6) What food or treats does he/she like the most?

7) Is there any food that he/she reacts badly to (heartburn, diarrhea, itching, or restlessness)?

- No Yes (what food?).....

8) How often does he/she touch your food?

- Never Rarely Sometimes Almost always

9) When food is available:

- Eats slowly Plays with/spreads food Eats quickly and greedily
 Guards the dish (growls, defends)

10) Does he/she share his food with others (humans or other animals)?

- Yes No It depends

11) Do you use treats or ready-made treats?

- No Yes: a) Type or brand:
 b) frequency: Sometimes Daily Several times a day

12) How much water does he/she drink?

- A lot Average Little Very little / almost never drinks

13) Is a water source always available?

- No Yes

14) Has the type of food, brand, or diet recently changed?

- No Yes (please explain):

15) Has there been a recent change in water or food consumption patterns?

- No Yes (please explain):

Section Seven:

1) Have you ever brushed his/her teeth?

- No Yes (please specify): a) How often? Daily Several times a week Sometimes
b) With what tool? Special toothbrush and toothpaste Tissue / gauze Other:.....

2) How often does his/her mouth smell bad?

- Never Sometimes Often Always

3) Have you ever observed any of the following? (*You can select more than one option*)

- Bleeding gums Redness or swelling of the gums Dental tartar or discoloration
 Loose or falling teeth Pain when chewing None

4) Has he/she ever undergone dental scaling/dental procedures?

- No Yes (how often and when):

5) Does he/she exhibit any of these behaviors? (*You may select more than one option*)

- Chews food one-sidedly Takes food but drops it Paws at its face or mouth
 Reacts when its mouth is touched Prefers soft foods None

6) Have you noticed any recent changes in his/her chewing or oral behaviors?

- No Yes (Please explain):

Section eight:

1) How long does he/she usually stay alone during the day?

- Not at all Less than 2 hours 2 to 4 hours 4 to 8 hours
 More than 8 hours Several days

2) Where does he/she usually stay when he/she is alone?

- Free in the whole house A specific room Cage / confined space Yard
 Aquarium / enclosure I don't know / I haven't noticed Always accompanied

3) How does he/she react when you want to leave the house?

- Indifferent Follows me Gets restless Makes noises
 Tries to block the exit Hides Other:

4) How does he/she usually behave when you return home after a while?

- Very excited and enthusiastic Calm but happy Indifferent
 Gets angry/pulls away Shows aggression Takes a while to calm down

5) Have you encountered any of the following when left alone? (*You can choose multiple options*)

- Urinating or defecating in inappropriate places Damages household items
 Makes noises/screams/long sounds Licking or biting yourself
 Trying to escape None

6) Have neighbors or people around you ever complained about his/her noise or behavior when you were away?

- No Yes (please explain):.....

7) After you have been away for a long time, does he/she:

- Overly clingy Irritable Aggressive Needs a lot of attention
 No unusual behavior

8) How much does he/she insist on sleeping next to you or entering your personal space?

- Not at all Sometimes Often Always

9) When you are away for a long time, does he/she:

- Stays alone Is entrusted to another person or place: Animal's reaction: Easily adjusts
 Gets stressed
 Shows unusual behaviors

10) In recent weeks or months, have you noticed any particular changes in his/her behavior when he/she is alone or when you return?

- No Yes (please explain):

Section Nine:

1) How much does he/she usually lick or groom himself/herself?

Don't know Very little Normal A lot

Excessive and repetitive: Which areas of the body are most affected?

2) Have you ever seen he/she bites himself/herself?

No Yes, sometimes Yes, frequently: a) Which areas of the body?

b) Has he/she resulted in a wound or hair/feather loss? Yes No

3) Has he/she ever pulled out his/her own hair or feathers?

No Yes, sometimes Yes, frequently: a) Which areas?.....

b) Since when?

4) How much does he/she scratch himself/herself?

Rarely Sometimes A lot Always and frequently

5) If there is itching, which area is most affected?

6) How much does he/she play with his/her tail or show unusual attention to it?

Never/rarely Sometimes A lot Obsessively (chasing/biting)

7) How does his/her react to the mirror or his/her own image?

Indifferent Curious Playful Aggressive Scared

Not paying attention/Don't know

8) Which of the following behaviors have you observed recently? (*You can choose multiple options*)

Continuous licking of a spot Spinning around Continuous shaking of a leg or head

Sudden biting of the body and releasing None

9) If any of the behaviors listed above are present, when are they most commonly seen?

Never When alone At night When stressed After a lot of excitement

No specific time Don't know

10) Have these behaviors been observed in recent weeks or months:

Not observed Constant Increased Decreased Newly started

11) In your opinion, the behaviors asked about in this section (such as constant licking, biting yourself, etc.):

Are normal Are worrying Not sure

Additional explanations:

Section Ten:

1) What is his/her usual activity level?

- Very inactive Moderate Very active Hyperactive
 Variable (very active some days, lethargic some days)

2) How much noise does he/she make? (species specific noises)

- Very little Sometimes A lot Annoying/constant

3) In what situations is the noise usually more?

- Alone Playing Presence of strangers Food At night Uncertain

4) Has he/she ever shown aggressive behavior?

- No Yes, sometimes Yes, frequently: To whom?.....

5) How does he/she show aggression?

- Biting Grabbing Sudden attack Growling/roaring/screaming
 Non-contact warning only

6) Has he/she ever bitten or grabbed someone?

- No Yes: a) How often?

b) Has it resulted in injury? Yes No

c) Usually in what circumstances? Play Fear Pain Defending food/territory Not sure

7) How often does he/she: a) Follow people? Never Sometimes Often

b) Chase objects or shadows? Never Sometimes Often

8) Has he/she ever suddenly reacted violently without any clear warning?

- No Yes (please explain):

9) Have you ever noticed any obvious changes in his/her mood?

- No Yes Please select: Happy and playful periods Periods of lethargy or withdrawal

Extreme fluctuations throughout the day Sudden change from the past

10) How often does he/she listen to you?

- Very good Average Poor Never

11) Has he/she had training or a trainer?

- No Yes (what kind of training):

12) How often does he/she not do what you tell them to do or intentionally do the opposite?

- Never Sometimes Often

13) How do you usually respond when he/she misbehaves?

- Ignore Verbal warning Removal from the situation Physical punishment
 Rewarding methods

14) Has he/she ever been punished?

- No Yes, sometimes Yes, frequently
In what way?

15) What is his/her level of curiosity?

- Low Average High

16) Have you noticed any specific behavioral changes in the past few weeks?

- No Yes (please explain):

Section Eleven:

1) Has he/she ever had any of the following? (*If yes, please specify time and number*)

a) Movement and activity:

- Limping or inability to bear weight on one arm or leg
 Extreme tiredness or sudden stop while playing or running
 Decreased desire to move or play
 None

Time/Explanation:

b) Digestion and appetite:

- Loss of appetite or poor appetite
 Unusual overeating
 Vomiting
 Diarrhea
 Constipation
 Severe bloating or abdominal pain
 Eating non-food items (dirt, feces, wire, cloth, etc.)
 None

Time/Explanation:

c) Urine and stool:

- Change in urine color
- Change in stool color or consistency
- Increased or decreased frequency of urination
- Straining during bowel movements
- Urinating or defecating in inappropriate places (unusual compared to before)
- None

Time/Explanation:

d) Skin, hair and feathers:

- Severe shedding or Abnormal hair/feathering
- Excessive itching
- Sores or inflamed areas of skin
- Frequent licking or chewing of a specific area
- Dragging the pelvic area on the floor
- None

Time/Explanation:

e) Eyes, ears, mouth:

- Discharge or redness of the eyes
- Unusual tearing
- Bad breath
- Bleeding gums
- Discharge or itching of the ears
- Excessive or abnormal salivation
- None

Time/Explanation:

f) Breathing:

- Difficult or rapid breathing
- Wheezing or unusual sounds
- Frequent sneezing or coughing
- Unusual discharge from the nose
- None

Time/Explanation:

g) Neurological symptoms

- Muscle tremors
- Unusual muscle twitching
- Loss of balance
- Tilting of the head or neck
- Drooping lip or eyelid
- Tongue sticking out
- Seizures or abnormal movements
- None

Time/Explanation:

h) Sexual Status:

- If female: Changes in breasts Abnormal discharge Changes in estrus
- Abnormal sexual behavior None
- If male: Changes in urination behavior Excessive marking
- Abnormal sexual behavior None

Time/Explanation:

i) Lumps:

- Palpation of an unusual lump or bump on the body
- Pain when touched
- Local swelling
- None

Time/Explanation:

2) Are any of these symptoms currently ongoing?

- No Yes (which ones?):

Section Twelve:

1) What do you think is the most important problem or concern with him/her?

(If there is more than one, list in order of importance)

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

2) When did you notice this problem or change?

- Less than a week 1–4 weeks Several months Long term (more than 6 months)
 Not sure No problem

3) Is this problem:

- Improving Remaining the same Getting worse Comes and goes No problem

4) Do you think this change or problem is related to a specific event?

- No problem No problem No problem Yes (please explain):

5) Have you ever done anything about this problem?

- No problem No Yes (please explain):

6) What do you expect from this visit? (*You can choose multiple options*)

- Complete physical examination Behavioral examination
 Guidance to reduce stress or fear Advice and guidance only
 Improving his/her relationship with the family Treatment for a specific problem
 Other:

7) Is there anything else you think is important to know that is not mentioned in the questions above?

- No Yes (please explain):

Questionnaire II

**Dear Doctor,

Based on your observations and review of the results of the first form, please enter your comments and diagnosis in the form below

Thank you**

(This section is completed by the veterinarian, independent of the referral form)

Section One:

Veterinarian Observations During Current Visit

- Completely Normal Animal Behavior in the Clinic
- Mild Anxiety
- Moderate Anxiety
- Severe/Uncontrollable Anxiety
- Aggression
- Fear
- Withdrawal
- Restlessness
- Suspicious Pain
- Repetitive Behaviors
- Inconsistency Between Patient's Statement and Observed Behavior

Brief Explanation (if needed):

Section Two:

Items extracted from the client form (based on the answers given)

- Feeding problems
- Digestive problems
- Skin problems / itching
- Sleep disorders
- Separation anxiety
- Domestic aggression
- Recent behavior change
- Inadequate maintenance / insufficient information from the client

Section Three:

Initial Clinical Summary (*Treating Veterinarian Analysis*)

- Predominant Veterinary Problem
- Predominant Behavioral Problem
- Combined Problem (Psychosomatic)
- Primary Maintenance/Training Problem
- Need for Further Investigation

Section Four:

Proposed Referral Pathway (*more than one option may be selected*)

- Continue follow-up by attending veterinarian at/in
- Referral to department veterinarian
- Referral to laboratory
- Referral to maintenance training department
- Referral to behavior/training trainer
- Referral to other (specialty) clinic
- No referral/follow-up required

Explanation for department referred:

Section Five:

Non-medical education required by the client (*if needed*)

- Nutritional principles
- Housing and environment principles
- Correct interaction with the animal
- Anxiety management
- Sleep and play schedule
- Non-punishment training
- No training required
- Referral to the training department
- Brochure/protocol delivered
- Completed/Done (*to be selected by the training department*)

References supporting the development of this questionnaire:

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4. Kenneth M. Martin, Debbie Martin, Julie K. Shaw, *Small Animal Behavioral Triage: A Guide for Practitioners, Veterinary Clinics of North America: Small Animal Practice, Volume 44, Issue 3, 2014, Pages 379-399, ISSN 0195-5616, ISBN 9780323297295, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cvsm.2014.01.004>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0195561614000059>)*
5. Camps T, Amat M, Manteca X. A Review of Medical Conditions and Behavioral Problems in Dogs and Cats. *Animals (Basel)*. 2019 Dec 12;9(12):1133. doi: 10.3390/ani9121133. PMID: 31842492; PMCID: PMC6941081.
6. Lloyd JKF. Minimising Stress for Patients in the Veterinary Hospital: Why It Is Important and What Can Be Done about It. *Vet Sci*. 2017 Apr 13;4(2):22. doi: 10.3390/vetsci4020022. PMID: 29056681; PMCID: PMC5606596.
7. Yusuf H, Hillman A, Stegeman JA, Cameron A, Badger S. Expanding access to veterinary clinical decision support in resource-limited settings: a scoping review of clinical decision support tools in medicine and antimicrobial stewardship. *Front Vet Sci*. 2024 Jun 4;11:1349188. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2024.1349188. PMID: 38895711; PMCID: PMC11184142.